
Report on surface finds associated with two Roman villas near Bocholtz (NL)

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SURFACE FINDS ASSOCIATED WITH TWO ROMAN VILLAS NEAR BOCHOLTZ (NL)

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A final report about surface finds from field prospections in 2009 – 2015

**SURFACE FINDS ASSOCIATED WITH TWO ROMAN VILLAS NEAR BOCHOLTZ (NL) A REPORT
ABOUT FIELD - PROSPECTIONS FROM 2009 - 2015**

Samenvatting in Nederlands

Tijdens verschillende veld prospecties, die in de jaren 2009/2010 en 2014/2015 zijn uitgevoerd, zijn veel oppervlaktevondsten verzameld, welke in dit verslag ter documentatie zijn opgenomen. Oppervlakte vondsten zijn niet de meest favoriete objecten in de archeologie, behalve bijvoorbeeld wanneer het fraaie of ongebruikelijke *ex situ* vondsten zoals bijzondere detectorvondsten uit perioden met een kennishiaat of bijvoorbeeld Neanderthaler botten zou betreffen, welke vondsten zelfs ook nog vaak eindigen in de vitrine van een museum. De reden waarom veel oppervlakte vondsten hier wel gedocumenteerd zijn, is het feit dat deze zeer duidelijk gerelateerd kunnen worden aan locaties waarover veel is bekend, in dit geval aan bekende Romeinse villa complexen. In de vier delen van dit verslag, zijn vondsten beschreven en opgesomd, met speciale aandacht voor de mozaieksteentjes uit de Romeinse tijd, gevonden op een locatie in het meest zuidoostelijke deel van het onderzochte gebied. Tijdens de prospecties is ook aandacht besteed aan mogelijke metaalvondsten, welke als oogvondsten zijn meegenomen. Andere vondstgroepen worden gevormd door aardewerk, glasscherven en botfragmenten. Zoals te verwachten is in het geval van oppervlakte vondsten uit een bepaald gebied, kunnen slechts zeer algemene, op direct bewijs gefundeerde conclusies worden getrokken uit de vondsten, hetgeen aantoont dat dit verslag vooral beschouwd moet worden als documentatie van de verkregen informatie uit gerichte veldprospecties gedurende vier jaar.

Summary

During several field prospections, performed in the years 2009/2010 and 2014/2015, many surface finds have been collected, which are included and documented in this report. Surface finds are not the most favorite objects in archaeology, except e.g. when we deal with attractive detector- finds or unusual finds such Neanderthal bones, all found *ex situ*, which often end up in the showcase of a museum. The reason why many surface finds are documented here is the fact many of them are very obvious related to well known objects, i.c. Roman villa complexes. In the four parts of this report, finds are described and listed, with special attention to the mosaic stones from the roman period, found at a location in the most south eastern part of the investigated area. Other find groups include pottery, iron objects, glass fragments and ornaments. As expected from surface finds, found in a certain area, only very general, on direct evidence-based conclusions can be drawn from the finds, proving that this report mainly must be considered as a recording of obtained information during four years of targeted prospections. Full determinations will take some extra years.

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Part 1

FINDS FROM A LOCATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROMAN VILLA DELLENDER IN
BOCHOLTZ, (COMMUNITY OF SIMPELVELD, NL)

Part 2

FINDS FROM A LOCATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROMAN VILLA VLENGENDAAL
IN BOCHOLTZ, (COMMUNITY OF SIMPELVELD, NL)

Part 3

TESSERAE FOUND AT A LOCATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROMAN VILLA VLENGENDAAL
IN BOCHOLTZ, (COMMUNITY OF SIMPELVELD, NL)

Part 4

SOME COMPARISONS BETWEEN FINDS ASSOCIATED WITH VLENGENDAAL (VA) AND DELLENDER
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1. Introduction

One hundred years after the publication on the excavations of the Roman villa Vlengendaal by Goossens in 1916, the witnesses of Roman presence in this area are still more than present. Archaeological field- prospections are made with a purpose: the discovery of new archaeological traces, which can be embedded in existing knowledge, or in the best case, would add some new information. In some cases, prospections might have an additional advantage: salvaging any remaining vulnerable objects from a context in which the material is experiencing rapid weathering or degradation, by activities such as ploughing, intense fertilizing, frost, etc. A plurality of field prospecting conducted in different years in the area of Bocholtz has yielded a relatively large amount of archaeological material, mainly from the Roman period.

The archaeological information about Roman occupation in the south eastern part of South - Limburg is relatively big and well described in several papers (Goossens, 1930; Braat, 1948; De Groot, 2006, 2007) and gives a general impression about roman life in this part of South - Limburg.

In this case, the Roman villa *Vlengendaal* located in the southeast of Bocholtz (at a location named "*In den Berg*") has been studied most and obtained most information, as remains of this complex had been excavated in 1911 and 1913 (Goossens, 1912, 1916) while a possible link has been noticed between a nearby found Roman sarcophagus, which has been excavated in 2003 (De Groot, 2006).

The villa complex of *Dellender*, (German: *Butterweiden*) located east of Bocholtz, has been partially excavated in 1992 (Van Haaff, 1992). The excavation revealed some fundamentals of a building, interpret as a roman villa. As the remains of this villa complex are located at both sides of the Dutch-German border, the function of this building complex building had been diffused by the German opinion of the archaeologist Wagner, suggesting the building would have (partially?) served as a temple., while later the function had been noted as a part with four working rooms and a living space, similar to the southern corner tower of the *Vlengendaal* villa. A possible local graveyard and several indications about Roman roads have been established in the nearby area, so we might deal with a small Roman village ("road"- village, in Dutch: "*wegdorp*"). The found archaeological correlate discussed in this paper is not about treasures, but all about rubbish and demolished, weathered *out of context* objects. Yet this correlate contains sufficient information that is discussed below.

2. Research questions

Two main questions are underlying the investigations:

1. Is there any clue about a possible extended habitation zone by the Roman's in the specific part of the possible settlement, located east of the village Bocholtz?
2. Is there any clue about continuity in habitation, or about pre - Roman habitation in this part of the region, especially in relation with the landscape?

3. Methods

For archaeological information in this area, literature is available about several excavations that took place in the past (Goossens, 1930; Braat, 1948; De Groot, 2006, 2007). Many objects have been found over the very long period of investigations in the area, of which some discoveries were already made in 1871 by Habets (182901823).

Such surface survey could provide information about the period of use of buildings and its possible function; if the discoveries would be determinable and linked to a certain position in the field; especially in possible relation with existing archaeological information (see e.g. Bevan et al., 2012). Patterns, discovered by surface survey, generally are highly unreliable to explain detailed (local) spatial distribution patterns, any reconstruction based on surface finds always has to be regarded as a general overview of the outcome of the prospections with possible corresponding information (see e.g. Banning, 2002). This is also because the collected material only reflects a minor part of what is below the surface horizon and which is rotated and moved all time the field is ploughed (Horobik and Parkisons, 2007). In this case, a part of the investigations focused on specific find zones, but as this also highly is dependent on geological processes (apart from the disturbed contexts) the outcome does of course not at all provide a clear view on the original (Roman) situation. So, it was clear the information from a surface survey would be limited to global impressions, though a direct link to existing archaeological site information from literature could justify some further investigations in regard to the discovered archaeological correlate at the surface. The same is in count for the *numbers* of finds, especially within certain determined find categories, as this is highly depending on what has been ploughed up by accident and what is visible at the moment of the prospections (within conditions of e.g. intensity of (day) light, reflections and moisture of the soil, the soil type and

contrast, experience of the prospector, etc.). For this reason it was decided to do a field survey in a multiannual plan, also to adjust and deepening prospection strategies, based on obtained information from previous prospections and obtain more information from 'hotspots' (this provided e.g. a very rare, unique small *decorated* Terra sigilata fragment). The numbers of artefact types, such as numbers of specific potter - types or type of iron objects might give an *indication* about relationships between the objects and its certain location, while in the best case it can be linked to a special period. The latter requires very well datable objects, which is often already a problem during excavations (Greene, 1992; Cau, Reynolds, and Bonifay, 2011).

For this reason a quantitative sampling method was necessary, because this could potentially provide information about both relative *numbers* of utensils, and specific determinable *details* of shards of fine- pottery, typical rim- shards or small glass – fragments, all related to a certain sub Roman period. In this case, it would be possible to make some comparisons between finds from two separated locations that are associated with known Roman villas, i.c. villa *Vlengendaal* and villa *Dellender*; immediately considering this outcome is of course always subject to (some) restrictions (see part 4 of this report).

3.1 Methods: field prospections

For the detection of surface finds, several targeted field prospections were carried out in 2009 and 2010 and then in 2014 and 2015, coincident with the authors domicile. The alternating visits to different fields are connected with the accessibility of the terrain, wheatear conditions and available time for prospections. In total, six different locations have been prospected. The prospected locations were pre- selected by study of its position in the paleo-landscape zone east of Bocholtz, indicating former water source areas in drained zones, protected by (north-) east oriented winds, which can be very cold in winter at the highest parts of the plateau. This situation is the case for both B4 and B1. Fields were systematically searched by field walking in parallel rows of ca 1 meter width. Thus, either by finding single finds or by concentrations of archaeological correlate or changing soil structures made a more targeted prospection strategy possible see figure below.

Simple prospection strategy to focus on finds from concentrations, especially for very small objects like microliths, tesserae, etc. A: the whole field is systematic walked in rows; B: concentrations of finds are noticed C: targeted prospections on concentrations D: within the area of find concentrations targeted prospections are carried out for specific information (Arbannig, prospection strategies, 2011)

The whole zone at location B4, where a typical dark colored soil type is exposed had been systematic sampled. The focus of the prospections was limited by sampling possible finds that could give clues about the function of the inhabited zone, so several types of finds were deliberately neglected, such as natural stones, building materials and roof tiles parts, though from the latter type it is possible to even distinguish differences in thickness and fabrication process.

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The methods in the objective also are limited to possible field inspections in the available area; like all non built-up areas, further limited by its accessibility of terrains depending on (temporary) land-use (forest, crop- rotation, grasslands). The fields were coded B (= Bocholtz) with additional numbers and possible finds from the roman period were labeled either Vlengendaal Associated (VA) or Dellender Associated (DA), see in table below.

Field	Coordinates N/E*	Fieldname	Country	Association
B1	50 48 45 9/ 6 01 13 6	Dellender	NL	DA
B2	50 48 2 1 /6 01 16 7	Dellender	NL	DA (?)
B3	50 48 43 4/ N 6 00 37 7	-	NL	-
B4	50 48 12 3 / 6 00 25 5	Vlengendaal	NL	VA
B5	50 48 25 4/ 6 00 38 2	Vlengendaal	NL	VA
DB1a	50 48 41 9/ 6 01 20 3	<i>Butterweiden</i>	D	DA

* Coordinates by Google Maps, with minor discrepancies up to ± 20 m

Table 1: Prospected fields and some additional information

As contexts are disturbed by plowing activities, only global spatial patterns about finds could be available, so exact measurement by GPS was not necessary. In some cases some spatial data recordings have been made, e.g. for special finds (see maps in appendix).

The disturbance of the context generally is a primary problem in the use of field inspections as a reliable method in archaeological investigations; in the paragraph of the specific investigated locations this problem is discussed for each location.

Because of severe law in Germany (the so called "Schatzregal DSchG" in NRW) all archaeological observations from the German part (*Butterweiden*) were only field recorded, and arbitrary documented later, without further collection. The reason to field walk this part was to notice possible deviant pottery shards compared with those found in the Dutch part. As the result of the field walking in Germany only gives some confirming, extended information about the Dellender location at the Dutch side of the border and does not give real new information it has been added to this report for completeness and possible interpretation of the extended, more extensive "Dellender" location.

Figure 1: Map of the environment of Bocholtz, with prospected locations visible on the map east of Bocholtz, corresponding with the numbers 1-5. The field with code DB1a is in Germany. Map by Google Maps 2009-2014.

2009		B2		B4	
2010	B1		B3		
2014	B1	B2		B4	B5 / DB1a
2015	B1			B4	

Table 2: The prospected terrains in East Bocholtz and years of inspections

3.2 Methods: determinations

The determination of pottery is based upon the Tongeren Reference Collection (VIOE report 01) and some literature ((Hiddink, 2014; publications of the LVR in Germany and a copy of the Potshard Atlas), see references in the text. Only main groups and types have been determined.

In practise, this means, inexperienced in determination of pottery types, choices had to be made, as the descriptions from various literature are in a way contradictory: e.g. a shard in smooth white fabric belonging to an amphora fits in both *smooth ware* and *amphora* and a coarse shard could be classified as *coarse ware* or, if belonging to a *mortarium* in the *mortaria* group. In this case the shards were placed into groups as amphora, *mortaria* and *dolia*, referring to the function.

Stylistic determination of pottery is based upon form, fabric and decoration, which might help to identify variety in pottery from a location for a certain period. Generally, information about individual pots can be obtained by counting or weighing shards belonging together (similar fabric) but this could give imbalances in the outcome. So, the numbers of shards determined by fabric (technology in relation with clay) are only indicative for this group in relation with other groups and are only to be interpreting with additional information about the function of the pottery. Descending by fabric is in this case a helpful tool for further determination. The bulk of shards (undecorated body shards) have been sorted by the naked eye, regarding inclusions, absence of temper, smooth surface, color of the fabric, etc. The outcome is a number of groups, which is based on fabric instead of type: this means e.g. shards of amphorae produced in the same fabric as jars are placed in the same group. Rim shards, bottom shards, handles and decorated body shards could provide information about pottery type and function (e.g. vessel, plate, jar, amphora, etc.), about size and content and the period based on the typo- chronology. Shards too small to identify or of uncertain date were listed as undated. Many in itself diagnostic shards were either transversely broken or crumbled in several places or very small, so determination was not always possible. For macroscopic features of glass-objects, pottery shards and mortar a binocular with magnification up to 5 x has been used. For colour standards of pottery and tesserae the *Munsell* chart has been used.(result in updated version in the future).

3.3. Methods: reporting

This report is mainly reporting, listing and illustrating the surface finds from the small investigated region, east of Bocholtz. Normally in regional archaeology, a short list of surface finds would be sufficient. Intentionally, it is chosen for an extensive view of the results, notwithstanding the fact that we 'only' deal with surface finds, which are generally less valuable compared with finds from regular excavations. However, the direct link between nearby excavated terrains makes it worth to write this extensive report, which at the same time explains why so many illustrations and tables are listed in this report. In all cases this is a trade-off between significance of certain finds and available space particularly due to specific find categories which have been more intensively examined, like pottery, mosaic stones and glass finds. In this case, pottery is always one of the most interesting find groups while Roman mosaic stones are to be considered as very special finds in the Netherlands, even individual finds from surface contexts, so are sufficiently important to be described and enumerated in detail (see also Vanhoutte and Vanderhoeven, 2007).

4. The investigated area: some general information

The find location has an altitude of ca + 190 m. a.s.l. (N.A.P.) and is located near a large depression in the field, which is in continuation with a valley sloping down into the northern direction, where it once was a main drain of the wider source area of the local brook named *Eijserbeek*.

The current source area of the Eijserbeek can be found in the zone north west of Bocholtz, at an altitude of ca + 160 m a.s.l. . It is very well possible and likely Roman villas were constructed at locations where a water spring was available for fresh water supply. An adequate water spring was the primary site-location factor for a villa, besides of the availability of natural resources, fertile grounds and a good communication and defense network (Oltean, 2007; Verhagen and Drăguț , 2009). Deep wells were often dug to ensure enough drinking and cleaning water for the family, laborers and livestock. Such local, manmade drain systems in the vicinity of running water has been established at many locations in the Roman Empire (see e.g. Blair et al. 2006) and this is also known for the region, like at the villa *Bovenste Caumer* next to the spring of the Caumerbeek in Heerlen (Peters, 1930 and at the Roman villa of Voerendaal (Willems, 1988). Similar locations fit in a broader Empire economy through a system of secondary (and tertiary) Roman roads, such as is the fact in Bocholtz. Besides of the water supply, the provenance of relatively hard limestone, locally named *Bocholtzer steen*, for the foundation of houses and roads was important. The roman watch tower, once located at the top of the nearby hill, known as the *Schneeberg* in the adjacent German Aachen – region at ca three kilometers distance, would have played a major role in the security for the Roman inhabitants of this area.

Figure 2: Map of the source/ drain area of the Eijserbeek at Bocholtz and locations of established or possible locations of Roman villas (red dots), projected on an elevation map (by AHN2, open data source, local range +156. 3 - +195.5 a.s.l.). Numbers 1 - 5 possible pre- and protohistoric sources: 1. Location where a Roman villa at Orsbacherweg is suspected; 2. Vast depression areas next to villa Vlengendaal; 3. Drain area next to villa Dellender, where parts of drain pipes have been found; 4. Drain from the higher zone of the Akerweg, where after rainfall water is running for days or even weeks; 5 a remarkable straight drain from the current Avantis area. Light blue star= suspected villa O= Orsbacherweg ; blue star = established villa: V= Vlengendaal and D= Dellender.

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Figure 3: The locations of B1 = Bocholtz 1, B2 and DB1a= Butterweiden in Germany which is the zone where roof tile parts and many pottery shards were noticed; B1 is Dellender associated investigated area, B2 the elongated area with roof tile parts. Map adapted after AHN elevation map and coordinates taken by Google maps).

Figure 4: The location of B1 photographed from the Helweg. The investigated part of the field is marked in the white brace.

8. The location B1, DB1a and B2 (Dellender Associated DA)

The investigated area near the location of the Roman villa named Dellender is split into three locations:

1. the terrain directly adjacent to the Roman villa site (B1) in the Netherland
2. the terrain north of the railway incision, adjacent to the Roman villa site (B2) in the Netherlands
3. the terrain east of the Roman villa site (DB1) which is separated from the (excavated) villa location by an artificial wall (landform of the border of the German town Aachen) in Germany

Decisive factor for the investigated area was the presence of Roman roof tile parts and accompanying Roman pottery shards at the surface. It appears, the area of Roman Dellender was probably much larger than earlier thought. Indeed, Roman roof tile parts are spread over a large surface, at both sides of the border. The locations B1 and B2 are separated by a deep incision of the railway, and could be regarded as a continuation of the same area, where a flared slope is visible at both fields. Indeed, roof tile parts appeared in this zone at B1 and B2.

9. Finds from B1 and descriptions

9.1. Pottery from B1

A limited Roman pottery determination in this report has been carried out with great caution, since errors at this stage could have far reaching consequences especially in making any comparison between the two inhabited zones (VA and DA, see part 4 of this report). As expected, no dating could be awarded to the material. The principal determination includes fabrics and quantities of shards, where fabrics were identified only macroscopically and were not sub-divided into different groups. Quantities were listed by determined fabric so the content of the assemblage and the relative occurrence of different fabrics and vessel types of the two different sites could be compared afterwards. If possible, form and function of individual pottery shards were determined as well. Other determination is carried out on surface decoration of pottery, wheel made or handmade pottery and special features.

a. Terra sigilata

b. Painted or color coated ware

Figure 5: Coated ware: right three shards of 'Cologne Coated ware' and left a small coated scale fragment in orange ware, probably from Trier.

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A total of 15 shards were found that fit in this group. Three of them are Cologne colored ware (KOL – CC, Dore and Tomber 1998). Two of these shards are decorated with parallel lines. The black coated bowl fragment, with its red- orange color likely originates from the kilns at Trier.

c. Coarse ware

Figure 6: Five rim shards of coarse ware (Eifelkeramik) from B1.

9.2. Terracotta pipe fragments, possibly used as water drain at B1

At field B1, many fragments of terracotta drainpipe have been noticed, but the connection with the roman period is *uncertain*. The distribution pattern in the field is suggesting fragments are from pipes, which have been in use as drain system, in *unknown* period.

Descriptions of drainpipe shards from B1.

The total number of shards of drainpipe is 32. The shards have been made of a hard terracotta fabric, in several color variations. Colors range between pale yellow orange (....) and some dirty gray (....). There is often a difference in color visible between the inner-side and outside of one shard, e.g. orange at the inside and pale yellow at the outside (probably not from the baking process, but a feature of weathering). The shards are also variable in size and many of the fragments show irregularity in wall thickness, which is ranging between ca 8 mm and 13 mm. The inner side of the shards is generally with a smooth surface, while the outside is more coarse, especially the flattened sides. Linear grooves occur at the outside of some shards. Shards were found in a large part of the field, ranging from almost the highest part till the lowest part, which is still marshy, especially after heavy rainfall. The pipe fragments were found over large part of the field, from the highest part into the direction of the lowest part of the field, which latter is not far from the railroad crossing at the Helweg. This is at least indicating it has not very likely the shards have been brought up with fertilizer; a relation with a building at the higher parts of the field cannot be excluded. The diameter of ancient terracotta drain pipes is ca 10 cm Finds from terracotta drainpipes in the wider region are known e.g. from Tongeren in Belgium , where a whole drainpipe has been found with features like thick-walled, undecorated, oxidizing, wheel -twisted with dimensions, Whole height: 26.50 cm (26.5 x 9.5 cm) Full width: 9.50 inches (26.5 x 9.5 cm) and dated between 057 and 450 AD (Erfgoedplus be ID= PGRM.objects.33367) and an incomplete water supply or (more likely) drain pipe in fine orange clay with gray core, in the context of a villa dated between 50- 250 AD (Erfgoedplus be - PGRM.objects.31960). The period for these shards is unclear. As the field is adjacent to the railway incision, there is always a chance the drain has been used during the building of the railway in the mid nineteenth century. It was indeed very important the excess water would not get into the track section of Bocholtz Vetschau.

Figure 7a: Drain pipe parts from B1 , ventral view, corresponding with the interior of the pipes

Figure 7b: Drain pipe parts from B1, dorsal view, corresponding with the exterior of the pipes

Figure 8: Map of field B1 with main positions of surface finds of terracotta drain - pipe fragments, showing its quasi -linear position in the field from east to west

9.3. Metal objects from B1

Some metal finds are reported here for completeness. Most objects are iron only few other metals have been found (i.c. bronze).

Figure 9: Fragment of a bronze fibula

Figure 10: Iron objects from B1. 1. Chisel. 2-6 Square nails 7. Part of an iron ring 8. Chain 9. ring shaped object 10. Wire with knot, for fixing window glass? 11. Hinge part? 12- 13 Indeterminate

Figure 11: Very thin copper wire, actually it is a bundle of wires, it has 12 loose ends. Relation with other finds is unclear.

9.4. Glass fragments from B1

Column 1	Color	length	width	thickness	Airbulb	features	validation
U1	very light green	30	18	15	present	melted glass fragment	likely
2	translucent	18	13	2	present		incerto
3	very light blue	21	19	3	present	modern appearance	likely
4	light green	23	11	4	present	ripples at one surface	likely
U5	black opaque	22				round, flat object diam. 22 mm, counter?	very likely
U6	blue greenish	18	17	10	present	rib?	very likely
U7	dark blue green	28	18	11	present	bottom part of bottle	likely
U9	Deep blue opaque					iron age bead 15/ 16 mm diam.	certain
U10	black opaque					bead diam of ring = 7.1 mm	likely
U11	dark green	11	6	2	present		incerto
U12	blue greenish	12	13	6	present	melted glass fragment?	likely
13	black opaque	20	11	10		infundibular shaped object	incerto

Table 3: glass finds from B1. Explanation see below

Glass finds from B1 (DA): explanations to the table (see above)

A total of 12 glass fragments is listed in the table. The original number of finds of glass fragments was 18. In this total (N=18) group, six glass fragments were determined as possible (sub-) recent glass, based upon its appearance (e.g. too thin, excessive shiny surface, etc.) and absence of weathering. All dimensions are in rounded millimeters.

For validation the following scale has been used

Characteristics: (1) find location, (2) appropriate color (blue- green- pale yellow), (3) thickness (at least 3 mm), (4) presence of air- bulbs (especially the elongated forms and position of the air-bulbs, e.g. in the lower parts of the object), (5) weathering features (craquelé, iridizing, corroded surface) and (6) surface patterns (wavy patterns, unevenness, small holes).

'very likely' (75%) at least 5 out of 6

'likely' (50 %) at least 4 out of 6

'incerto' 1- 3 out of 6

The category "incerto" is different from the glass that had been excluded in advance and still could be of the Roman period. As this scale is arbitrary and we deal with finds from the surface, a strict reservation is still required.

Details of some glass fragments.

U1 A melted glass fragment, very light bluish in color, containing very small and large air bulbs; at the broken part of the object numerous air bulbs are visible.

U5 A glass counter in black opaque glass with small attachment with traces of oxidized bronze, which is not exactly centralized in the object. Similar counters were found on top of the remains of a playing board at Lullingstone roman villa, in Kent (UK), where a complete set of thirty counters was discovered (see e.g. Crummy, 1995; Watson, 1998) and the same number has been found in a grave in Nijmegen (NL) (Van Enckevort, 2008). These counters would have been used for a game 'tabula' (Bell, 1979). The glass object is plano - convex in section and is 22 mm in diameter with a maximum thickness of 5 mm. The bottom surface is completely flat and matt, the upper side is shiny.

U6 A thick glass fragment containing a rib, with matt surfaces; possible it is a fragment of a ribbed bowl.

U7 Bottom fragment in typical Persian green color, belonging to a round shaped object, bottom thickness 3,0 mm, vertical wall thickness 3,0 – 4,3 mm.

U8 A bead in white opaque glass. In the glass very thin green lines are visible which have been melted during the production process. The bead is not regular rounded in shape and has a variable diameter in thickness (3.9 – 5.0 mm). It has been partially incised, probably to connect it to a pendant. The whole diameter is 7,5 mm.

U9 Dark blue opaque glass bead

U11 A melted glass fragment cf. In very light green blue color, containing rounded air bulbs, and with relatively sharp edges with adhered loess.

12 An opaque glass fragment in black color. It is funnel shaped, with a widest diameter (in extrapolation of ca 20 mm) and possesses a small whole at the smallest diameter, which is 9 mm. Possibly this is a counter of a board game.

Figure 12: Glass fragments from B1: 1. Melted glass fragment; 3. Flat green bluish colored glass fragment; 4. Fragment with ripples at surface 9. Blue opaque glass bead

Figure 13: Close-up of the bead (nr 9 previous image), showing glass properties and weathering. It measures (DIM)

Figure 14: Glass objects and fragments from B1: 5.glass counter, 6. glass with rib, 7. bottom part, 8. white opaque bead (Iron Age)

Figure 15: Glass finds from B1: 11. Melted glass fragment, 12. Round object in black opaque glass

Figure 16: Glass finds from B1: a-e, indeterminate

IMAGE G13 C

(to be inserted)

*Glass finds from B1: cat. nr. G 13 C small fragment (top rim) of a free blown colorless glass globular bottle, 3rd – 4th century AD, reference "Bottle [Roman]" (17.194.317) In Heilbrunn Timeline of Art History . New York: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2000–.
<http://www.metmuseum.org/toah/works-of-art/17.194.317>. (October 2006)*

9.5. Bone from B1

Bone material, found on the surface, usually is a very unreliable in terms of the period. The collected bone fragments sometimes have intense glossy patinas, probably indicating a higher date, but still the relation with other finds is unclear. Finds of several fragments of oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) could have a relation with the villa; they are absent at the Vlengendaal associated area and do not occur frequently in the fields. No conclusions are to be drawn from the above mentioned material which is listed here only for completeness.

Figure 17: Bone fragments and molars from B1. In the top right section the bones have a polished shiny surface, while the bone fragment right left has been signs of being burned. All pieces are definitely more or less fossilized (in a fire test)

Figure 18: Fragment of an oyster (Ostrea edulis)

Figure 19: Painted lime fragments from B1.

9.6. Natural stone from B1

A single fragment of marble has been found at location B1. If it is really related to the other roman finds is unclear.

Figure 20: A fragment of marble, found at B1. Left front view, right section view

10. Finds from B2 and descriptions (DA)

Field B2 is the elongated part of field B1, in the northern direction, separated by the incision of the railway between Simpelveld and Vetschau. The field is characterized by its large flattened zone, with a well visible elevation. It has two entrances from the *Akerstraat*, which serve and served as possible drains; the *Akerstraat* itself is still aquiferous after prolonged rainfall.

Only a part of this field has been prospected by reason of accessibility (caused by changing land-use); the location has been visited six times. Roman roof tile parts were noticed only at a very limited part of this field, and finds of pottery shards were made in the same section. The following finds are listed from B2:

10.1. Flint objects from B2

Six different flint artifacts all made of local flint type (Orsbach/ Vetschau horizons) have been found here. For descriptions and an image, see appendix 7. The flint artifacts could be regarded as the correlate of prehistoric activity by hunter gatherer groups, which visited the location. The broad period for these artifacts is estimated between the Mesolithic and late Neolithic period.

The artifacts were found at a very slightly sloping side of an elevation in the field, so probably there is more in this section.

10.2. Metal objects from B2

One iron object has been found, which is probably from the sub-recent period. It is not listed or described here.

10.3. Pottery from B2

The following pottery groups, based on shards, have been listed from B2

- | | |
|------------------------------------|---|
| a. Roman pottery | 4 shards (i. c. white colored and tempered) |
| b. Medieval pottery Pingsdorf-type | 2 shards |
| c. Early stoneware | 1 shard |
| d. Late stoneware | 7 shards |
| e. Red pottery | 1 shard |
| f. indeterminate | 5 shards |

10.4. Glass from B2

Two spherical glass fragments were found at B2, one is greenish and the other bluish in color; both fragments contain large numbers of tiny air bulbs. The estimated period for these fragments is Roman - Medieval.

11. Finds from DB1a (DA)

DB1 at the floodmap of Aachen (© by Floodmap Aachen) showing elevations at the field. In the projected area the colluvium part with gravels is visible in the pink colored zone, ZS = Zyklopensteine (large tertiary sandstones)

At field DB1a in Germany, locally known as *Butterweiden*, as an east- continuation of field B1 at the Dutch side of the border, many Roman roof tile parts are visible at the surface over an area of ca 100 x 50 m (see red dots in image above). These roof tiles are easily recognizable by its coarse temper, which consists of broken terracotta and coarse sands, its thickness (relatively thicker than later roof tiles) and shape (typical features from *tegulae* and *imbrices*). A colluvial horizon could be noticed at this field, running from a south - west to north – east direction, showing the location has been chosen for its position, protecting a part of the building complex at the upper part of the field against strong east oriented winds. The surface of the highest part of this field is covered with Pleistocene gravels mixed by dissolved flint and chunks of chalk, showing (prehistoric) erosion. Indeed, Roman pottery shards occur in the typical colluvial layer which appeared in a zone covering some 50 meters in the field, from *halfway* uphill to the south. Otherwise, the *presence* of roman roof tile parts were not limited to this zone, which could implicate many pottery shards are still buried in more deep horizons, whilst the original numbers of roof tile parts is very high, leaving them also in higher parts of the soil, where they were ploughed up. In the northern part of the field a large depression is visible, which, after intense plowing, is very moist. This depression could possibly be regarded a former spring zone, draining north. Finds from the surface are all made in relation with the colluvial soil, making the outcome somewhat unreliable. Indeed, at some places there is a mix of artifacts from many periods, ranging between the Roman period and present. Finds with a Roman date are

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limited to pottery shards, determined in the field, based on typical characterization of Roman pottery.

11.1. Finds from Butterweiden (Germany)

Finds from this field only belong to pottery. The following groups / fabrics were listed from DB!a (to be updated). Finds (observations) are including normal cookware like fragments of mortaria, Waasland type ceramics and Cologne coated ware.

Part 2 FINDS FROM A LOCATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROMAN VILLA VLENGENDAAL IN BOCHOLTZ, (COMMUNITY OF SIMPELVELD, NL)

12. The investigated area B4, B5 (Vlengendaal associated, VA)

Figure 21. The investigated area of B4 represented by the blue rectangular, approximately 50 x 40 m, in the orange area the find location of the tesserae and most glass fragments, approximately 20 x 30 m (image adapted from AHN viewer, coordinates from Google Maps)

The investigated area is located at 50.804659 N, 6.008512 E (± 20 m) in the community of Simpelveld, the Netherlands. In the map below, the investigated area is located in the extension of the Helweg, close to the German border. This location is forming a part of hamlet Vleengendaal, a southern extension of the village Bocholtz. The initially investigated area was a large field south east of Bocholtz in an extension of the Helweg. Once there has been noticed finds were exposed at the surface in a rather limited area exclusively related to a typical dark colored soil type, which can be interpreted as excavated and spread out soil (?) or moved soil (colluvium), this became the targeted prospection area (see image above, the colored rectangular). The soil type in this limited zone has a typical dense, greasy structure, known from highly by human activity influenced archaeological contexts. The soil type was containing many fragmented Roman roof tile parts, characteristic Roman pottery shards (e.g. fragmented *mortaria*), Roman window - and utensil glass fragments, wrought iron nails of the Roman type and many *tesserae*. The soil type is very distinct from the original more light colored loess cover (which is mixed by fragments of limestone, natural dissolved flint and bleached by underlying calcareous bedrock). In this typical dark colored soil type zone, that stretched over a large part of the field, also several field stones have been noticed, (in size up to 20 cm in diameter), and many limestone chunks with various dimensions, at some parts very fragmented.

In field prospections, fragmentation of limestone chunks could indicate former land use, where the highly fragmented lime chunks indicate a more intensive or longer land use compared with areas where the chunks have bigger dimensions. In the zone with highly fragmented limestone chunks, the *tesserae* *only* appeared at the surface when roof tiles were *very fragmented* and the *tesserae* finds were always accompanied by finds of Roman shards, iron nails and iron slag and an iron tool.

Besides of finds from the Roman period, only finds from the recent period (late 19th – 20th century) have been noticed, possibly indicating after excavations the terrain has been re-used for agricultural purposes, where these objects have been brought up from farms in the surrounding area.

6. Finds from B4 and descriptions.

Finds from B4 are categorized by type of material. These groups are: a) pottery, b) glass, c) metal, d) metal slag, e) bone and f) natural stone.

6.1 Pottery from B4

All surface finds attributed to the Roman period were determined by determination characteristics for the period, especially pottery shards, glass and stone *tesserae*, Roman glass and some special iron objects that are typical for the Roman period. At B4 several thousand pottery shards survived the ages, but only limited part of this group is suitable for further examination, these include especially rim – wall and bottom shards with special diagnostic features (especially by decoration, sometimes by special fabric type). So only this limited group of shards is involved in this report and all other shards are excluded. In the next part of this paragraph, the pottery shards of B4 are listed and described based on fabric and types. In the purpose of this report, it was not necessary and not always possible to subdivide all groups. Images and additional information of most interesting pottery shards can be found in the appendix of this report. In case of encoding, the reference code is referenced to the relevant pottery group or fabric.

6.1.1. Pottery of VA: fabrics

6.1.1.1. Terra sigilata

Terra sigilata (TS) is a luxury pottery; a red -gloss table ware, predominantly used for dating sites, as this pottery type has been present in the entire Roman Empire. The shards of Terra sigilata from B4 all are undecorated. One shard is relatively thick, and could belong to a mortarium.

Figure 22 .Rim shard of a cup in Terra sigilata with orange colored coating, with outward bent rim

Figure 23 A bottom fragment of a Terra Sigilata jug of Roman red ware, probably 3th century AD.
Left inner view, right outer view.

Figure 24 Various shards of Terra sigilata from B4, all undecorated

Figure 25 Very rare decorated fragment of Terra sigilata from B4

6.1.1.2. Terra nigra

A single decorated shard of terra nigra has been found.

Figure 26: Terra nigra shard with decoration

6.1.1.3. Color Coated wares (CCW)

Color Coated wares (CCW), which are luxurious fine ware, produced in local/ regional traditions of fine pottery comparable with TS sub divided into:

6.1.1.3.1. Cologne Color Coated ware (National Roman fabric reference collection code:KOL- CC)

The major part of shards of painted ware belongs to this group. A significant part of the fragments is decorated with lines, stripes and grooves. One fragment was conducted in typical barbotine, technique b, depicting a part of an animal head, where the eye and ear are still visible, type Niederbieber 32 (hunting), given the additional finds of rim shards of this type (Hiddink, 2014: 99); similar hunting figures are also known from England (Dore & Tomber, 1998).

The shards with a line- decoration exhibit different motives and are forming the second group. This group, mostly applied in technique b has besides of parallel carved patterns also motives in diamond form (hatched), scale shapes, and patterns of single elongated points. In this group the following shards have been determined

- a. wall shards with scale pattern (so called *barbotine*), thickness ca 1.8 mm, probably from a smaller jar type Stuart 1 N= 1
- b. wall shards with hatched pattern, thickness 3.9 mm, probably from a Stuart 4, N=
- c. wall shards with hatched pattern, thickness ca 3.9 mm but in technique a (painted dull reddish brown) Stuart 4 cf.
- d. wall shards with roughcasting (sand particles) in technique b, type Stuart 2 or Stuart 4
- e. rim shards, with outwardly curved edge with pointed shape, more or less spherical or straight rim – as continuation of the wall part (type Niederbieber30) (Technique after Brunsting, 1937).

Figure 27 Two shards of painted barbotine ware, left with scale motif, right an animal's head, (cat. a above)

Figure 28 Six shards of painted ware with roughcasting with sand (cat. d above) the more fine structure of roughcasting would be attributed to the Stuart 1 type) 1st century AD.

Figure 29 Decorated inner side of a painted ware pot, in technique c.

6.1.1.3.2. Color coated ware from Trier/ Argonne ("Moselkeramik "National Roman fabric reference collection code: MOS BS)

This group is different from the previous by its orange clay and glossier surface.

In this group, also some shards of "Qualitätsware" (technique d) occur in very low numbers. This type of pottery is easily recognizable by its (black) metal polish appearance and an orange core with grey/ black outside and inner side at visible at the fracture. Generally, four types can be distinguished:

- a) Shards in technique c, with orange till brown- orange colored clay with dull black coating
 - b) Shards in technique d, with orange core in grey in and outside, with glossy surface
 - c) Shards in technique d but *Terra nigra* like, in very hard pure grey fabric with glossy surface
 - d) Shards in technique d, in grey clay and with grey colored surface
- (Technique after Brunsting, 1937). All these types are very hard fabric.

Figure 30 A shard of *Qualitätsware* in a gray clay, with decoration, type Niederbieber 33

Figure 31 Shards of "Moselkeramik" in technique d, orange clay

Figure 32 Shards of "Moselkeramik" in technique d, grey clay with black coating or coating is missing or more grey

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Figure 33 A shard in technique d, but in grey clay, with hardly visible a decoration of parallel lines (slashes)

Table: determined shards in the group of Colour Coated ware

Type	Features	N
Stuart 1	Barbotine, scale	1
Stuart 2 /4	Roughcasting	
Stuart 4	Hatched pattern	
Niederbieber 30	Straight rim	
Niederbieber 32	Rim shard pointy; barbotine decoration (hunting)	1
Niederbieber 33	Metal gloss surface; tiny dashing	1

6.1.1.3.3 Painted ware

Figure 34 Shard of white fabric with painted decoration. Left inner side, right outside. Magnification of the painted shard in white fabric, showing the paint has been mixed with very fine black and brown particles, probably from volcanic origin.

6.1.1.4. Belgian wares (LLW)

- a) Terra nigra, blue grayish Roman ware; reduced baking pottery- black to gray, coarse tempered, “Low Lands Ware”, storage pots (1st- 3rd century AD)(BGRS)
- b) Terra rubra (Schelde valley pottery); oxidized baking pottery, (TRUBRA)

6.1.1.5. Grey ware (GW)

Grey to white pottery, in different hues

Some shards are decorated with a narrow undulating flange running around the vessel, although not the typical *mortaria* product this fabric probably belongs to the Mancetter-Hartshill type series.

- a) General Smooth ware (SW), white pottery with a very smooth surface and laminar structure most likely from Heerlen: storage jars and bowls for wine
- b) Rhineland Granular grey ware (Tongeren ref. collection code: RWGS-GG/RIJN). This group is formed by hard granular jugs, beakers, bowls and cups, probably smoked during firing process (Willems, 2005) The granular grey - type in this group is dominant at B4.

6.1.1.6. Course wares (CW) for cooking and food preparation and storage, are the most common wares

Figure 35 Two shards of Stuart 201 a course cooking pot. The decoration of grooves and bands generally was brought up at the upper part of the outer wall (Stuart 1977)

6.1.1.7. Smooth tempered ware from Rhineland (GWO- RIJN)

Finds from this group are shards from Rhineland jars

6.1.1.8. Indigenous Roman (IR),

This pottery has been made by local craftsman and it is unclear whether the pottery is imported from the nearby region or has been locally made, e.g. from the previous period, the Late Iron Age.

Remarkable, shards of handmade pottery at B4 were limited to the higher parts of the field, and most has been found outside the dark colored soil- type, which contained typical Roman pottery. Since all are surface finds, no further discrimination can be made.

Several shards are grog tempered pottery shards, crushed fired pottery of handmade (local?) pottery with dense inclusions, estimated till ca. 30 % in proportions of coarse fragments (Mathew, Woods and Oliver, 1991).

Figure 36 An example of a shard of grog -tempered ware from B4. These wares include models from black burnished wares, especially jars and bowls, but also dishes.

Figure 37 Detail of grog tempered ware, with inclusions of angular calcite fragments and pottery fragment, added as temper in a clay mix

6.1.2. Pottery of VA: Type

1. Mortaria (M), hemispherical and conical bowls often with coarse grits, used for pounding and mixing food
2. Dolia (D) used for mass - storage
3. Amphora's (A); used for storage and transportation of liquids

Several parts of amphora have been found at B4.

Two flattened base fragments of amphora were found at B4. The base shards are not from the same type of amphora, that could belong to the group of Gauloise flat-based amphoras , type Gauloise 5'

4. Cups or bowls

6.2. Glass and glass products from B4

6.2.1. Methods

For the determination of the glass finds, a binocular with magnification up to 10 x has been used. Vitreous mosaic stones have been measured, weighed, counted and described in color. Their Roman context is not really a point of discussion. Glass finds, discussed in this report however, have less solvency as determination only has been carried out by macroscopic properties of the glass (such as color, shape and presence of bubbles, surface patterns, weathering features; this also means the glass finds only could be placed in their possible period and – if possible- in a certain typology (e.g. window glass, fragment of a jar, etc.). In this case, a list of such features is listed in the corresponding paragraph.

Only few glass finds from the early twentieth century were mentioned in the report from Goossens during the excavations of from Vlengendaal (Goossens, 1916) and three of them have been described (as fragments of square bottles, Inv. no. 370 G. 6/ Inv. no. 370 G.7/ Inv. no. 370 G.IO and Museum Bonnefanten Maastricht cat. Nrs. 79, 80, 81, 13S, 152).

Already in the 1st century AD we find the first Roman window glass. The production technique of making such glass has gone lost, but has been carried out by experiments (see e.g. the experiments of Taylor and Hill, (Taylor, 2001)).

Roman window glass from the Netherlands is known from the villa of Voerendaal (Zoetbrood, 2005). At other domestic villa sites, like at Houten- *Oude Dorp* Roman window glass has been found. In the glass finds, several fragments could be determined as Roman window glass (see below). Roman glass is made of the same components as the later glass (soda - lime -silica), so for the identification this is useless.

6.2.2. Glass fragments: features

Roman glass was often recycled more than once, so the color changed from translucent into light green, bluish, etc. Besides of the color, ranging between blue, green there is also glass with brown-yellow color.

Several characteristic features were noticed in macroscopic examination of found glass fragments, which are interpret as Roman glass fragments, listed below (some of them are features only visible by a binocular with magnification of 4- 10 x)

1. Fragments are containing a range of bubbles, which are often rounded in shape, sometimes elongated, in that case mostly unidirectional positioned in the original direction of the flow of the glass. The presence of these bubbles often show regular unidirectional patterns and sometimes many very tiny bubbles for some sort of 'mini cloud'
2. There are sometimes differences in surface textures at both sides of one piece of glass, often one side is smooth, while the other is more crude, pointing at possible Roman window glass of the earlier phase of window glass production
3. The glass surface is containing small holes, often containing sand/ loess particles
4. The whole glass fragment is showing so called *craquelé* features, which could be partially both horizontally at the surface as vertically *in* the glass
5. The glass surface is sutured with sand or loess, sometimes at a big part of the surface, which cannot be removed by brushing
6. Some fragments have a typical wave pattern at the surface, where the wave lines run parallel
7. Tiny layers broken at the edges
8. Window glass often with rounded edges
9. A complete wave structure at the surface, where small depressions or bulges at the surface are visible; this is caused when the glass did not completely fill the mold during blowing.

Some of these features are presented in the pictures below

Figure 38 Craquelé feature (decomposed) on a Roman glass fragment; by influences of the soil, this fragment is in the process of saccharification (magnification 2 x)

Figure 39 Glass surface, sutured with sand or loess, weathering influence which cannot be removed by washing or brushing (magnification 2 x)

Figure 40 Glass surface with typical wave pattern of an iridizing flaw (prolapsed pattern) photographed in obliquely incident light (magnification 4 x)

Figure 41 Small air bubbles in glass. Air bubbles are no indication for Roman glass, but conversely Roman glass does very often contain air bubbles, especially elongated (magnification 2 x) The

'frozen' position of these elongated air bubbles could provide information about the direction of the foundry process.

Features that *do not* represent true characteristics for Roman glass:

1. Iridized glass fragments. This chemical reaction at the surface of the glass also might occur on later or even sub recent glass objects. Roman glass on the other hand is often more or less iridized, though very clear and modern looking fragments occur
2. A feature of expanded feather shape appears often on post -medieval glass.
3. Bubbles, which are air pockets in the glass, are not exclusive for Roman glass, but also appear in later medieval and post medieval glass. Elongated bubbles appear more often in Roman glass (fourth century window- panes : Whitehouse, 2003; elongated bubbles in crown glass, Martlew, 2007)

The determination of Roman glass is not always easy, especially in case of surface finds. For opaque glass this is not a big problem, but the translucent glass must have at least several features like listed above to classify them as Roman; this always in direct relation with the find location and/ or context of other finds from the Roman period. To consider these features is necessary because glass with an obvious post -Roman or even post -medieval date also has been noticed. In many cases, Roman glass has been determined by directions from its context (shards, coins, etc.). So, for the glass finds, described in this paper, some reservation is required, especially when it comes to 'colorless' translucent glass.

The colored glass fragments are different in size and color. Some fragments of window glass are relatively ' large ' regarding the period these objects were in the ground and the regular plowing activities over the decades.

The green colors are variable between light green and the more dark green type; some 'white glass' objects are of the opaque glass type and would therefore have been mixed by antimony (see e.g. Stern, 1995; Keller, Price and Jackson, -red.,2014)

6.2.3. Glass finds B4, descriptions

B4

... fragments of glass were found during the prospection years.

The glass fragments are divided into the following categories:

Colorless glass

Fragment greenish:

Fragments blue/green:

Fragments Bottle glass:

Fragments objects:

Fragments window glass:

The glass finds are labeled with G (Glass) with its find location B4(Bocholtz 4)

6.2.3.1. Window glass fragments

Roman window glass is relatively flat in appearance with the additional features

- a) In most of the cases, one side is smooth, the other coarse
- b) They show slight elongated shallow waves pattern, so have unequal surfaces
- c) Some fragments have rounded edges

Figure 42 Window -glass from the prospections in 2009

6.2.3.2. Utensil glass fragments

Fragments in this category are from bottles or other utensil objects.

Figure 43 Utensil glass from the prospections in 2009

Another fragment from B4 is of very light green glass, which is a flattened hollow rim part, containing tiny air bubbles of the Isings 44b type (characteristic is the flattened tubular shape, contrary to the 44a which is rounded in shape).

This Isings 4a type bowls or trays are hemispherical and have a stand ring and a characteristic outward and down turned hollow edge with a diameter of approximately 7 to 15 cm, while the b type are little more large in diameter (Isings, 1971; Catz & Van Litz, 2009). The period for this type of bowls has been established by Isings from many datable sites and has been set for the first century AD (Isings, 1957).

Figure 44 A hollow, flattened tubular rim fragment of a bowl from B4.

6.2.3.3. Jewelry.

Two very small opaque glass beads were found at B4. Because their period is very uncertain, they are stored in paragraph 9. Additional images of glass finds from B4.

6.2.3.4. Molten glass

Fragments of molten glass were found at the Vleengendaal associated location as well as at the Dellender associated location of B1. These fragments of molten glass do not necessary mean there has been a glass house (Isings, 1971), and there has been no proof for this at B4.

ID	Color	leng th	wi de	thickn Ess	M/G	Airb ulb	U/ W	R - edge	features	valida tion
W 1	Blue-greenish	42	23	4		present	W		craquelé	very likely
W 2	Blue-greenish	30	18	3		present	W			very likely
W 3	Blue-greenish	25	22	4		present	W		ribble	very likely
W 4	Blue-greenish	29	34	3		present	W			very likely
W 5	Blue-greenish	30	20	3		present	W	Pres Ent		very likely
U6	translucent	20	15	15		present	U		neck of bottle diam out 18 mm diam in 11 mm	incerto
W 7	Blue-greenish	23	20	4		present	W			very likely
W 8	Blue-greenish	19	15	4		present	W	cf	window pane glass?	very likely
W 9	Blue-greenish	34	22	4		present	W			very likely
10	translucent	40	40	4		present			surface with depressions	very likely
W 11	translucent	23	18	3		present	W	Pres Ent		very likely

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U1 2	translucent	14	33	4		present			craquelé	very likely
W 13	pale yellow	22	10	4		present	cf	W	window pane glass?	very likely
W 14	translucent	27	22	4		present	present	cf	W	window pane glass?
W 15	light green	52	26	5				present	W	both surface sides matt
16	Blue-greenish	20	11	12		present				melted glass fragment
W 17	Blue-greenish	32	20	5		present	present	W		Very Likely
W 18	Blue-greenish	27	22	3		present		W		Very Likely
U1 9	pale green	23	11	10				U	Bottom part square bottle rel.U31?	Likely
20	Blue-greenish	21	20	5		present				Very Likely
W 21	greenish	21	13	4		present	present	W	wave pattern surface	Very Likely
W 22	translucent	22	18	5		present		W		Very Likely
W 23	Blue-greenish	22	11	2,5		present		W		Very Likely
W 24	light green transl.	7	6	1,5		present	present	cf	W	window pane glass?
U2 5	blue greenish	20	15	2		present		U	elongated airbulbs	Very Likely
U2 6	blue greenish	10	9	6		present		U		Likely
U2 7	blue greenish	20	11	4				U	both sides matt. Melted?	Very Likely
U2 8	translucent	20	14	1,5		present		U	both sides matt	Likely
U2 9	translucent	13	12	5				U	rim shard cf. perfume bottle	Likely
U3 0	translucent	30	13	10		present		U	bottom shard cf. perfume bottle	Likely
U3 1	blue greenish	13	13	9		present		U	bottom part square bottle rel U19?	Likely
U3 2	blue greenish	18	10	2		present		U	concave; melted?	Likely
U3 3	translucent	29	13	5		present		U	craquelé	Likely
W 34	blue greenish	16	13	3		present		W		Very Likely
W 35	blue greenish	20	9	3		present	present	W		very likely
W 36	blue greenish	21	8	2		present	present	cf.	W	window pane glass?

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W 37	light green	14	10	3	pres ent	pres ent	W		very likely
W 38	light green	21	11	2	pres ent	pres ent	W		likely
W 39	green	21	13	1,5	pres ent	pres ent	cf W	window pane glass?	likely
U4 0	translucent green	17	7	5		pres ent	U	fragment of bottom of bottle cf.	very likely
W 41	blue greenish	10	9	3	pres ent	pres ent	W		very likely
42	light green	14	9	2	pres ent	pres ent			likely
43	light green	15	10	2,5	pres ent	pres ent	cf. W	window pane glass?	very likely
44	light green	15	8	2		pres ent			very likely
45	light green	12	10	2		pres ent			very likely
46	green	16	9	4		pres ent		corroded surfaces	very likely
47	green	13	10	3		pres ent			very likely
48	green	12	8	2		pres ent		corroded surfaces	likely
49	green	11	8	2		pres ent		corroded surfaces	likely
50	Light blue							bead	likely

Glass finds from B4 (VA): explanations to the table

A total of 49 glass fragments is listed in the table. The original number of finds of glass fragments was 67. In this total group, two glass fragments were determined as recent glass. For 16 glass fragments it was impossible to determine any period, they would fit in a post Roman period. Not all green glass with bulbs of course is Roman or Medieval. On the other hand, glass that might look modern could also be of a Roman date, depending on (local) taphonomic processes, which are unknown by the author. It looks like the glass fragment at B4 has suffered more from weathering compared to the glass finds at B1. In the table above, the vitreous tesserae are excluded.

The main groups of the glass fragments from B4 (N= 49) which are possibly with a Roman date are divided into window glass (W) and utensil glass (U).

The definition for window glass is mainly based on the different features of the surface of the glass, resp. matt and glossy at the same fragment, as a result of the production method of Roman pane glass (floating glass) where one side of the pane had strong contact with the floor which was covered with fine sand. An additional feature for this type of glass is a single rounded edge.

In the column G/M we find the presence or absence of different surface structures (Glossy/ Matt)

In absence of these properties, the other group is utensil glass; these are fragments of bottles and cups. All dimensions are in rounded millimeters. The color of the glass is variable, but many pieces show similar colors such as blue- greenish, in case the blue color was dominant. This arbitrary categorization in color is also meant as indicator of fragments that would fit in one original unit.

For the dimensions, the maximum dimensions are given. For its length and width, this means a triangle shaped fragment has its largest dimensions in the list, so the multiplied dimensions of both sides are not corresponding with its square surface. The thickness is rounded to whole millimeters.

In the description of the features, some additional information is given. One column is 'air- bulbs', to indicate if these are present in the glass fragment. Finally the fragments are roughly validated for the period. Determination of certain features was carried out with help of a binocular with 2 - 10 x magnification. In the column 'r - edge' the rounded edge of window glass fragments are listed.

All fragments were found in the dark colored soil type, which context would be related to the Vlengendaal villa., based on pottery finds, finds of wrought iron nails and other iron objects from the Roman period (chain, T- shaped nails) and mosaic stones. Still, this does not automatically attribute the glass fragments to the Roman period. This is why a simple scale has been used, based on both find circumstances and features of the glass fragment to come to some sort of cohesion for this material group.

One hundred percent validation is in theory impossible in case of surface finds. So the scale starts with 'very likely' (75%), based on (1) find location, (2) appropriate color (blue- green- pale yellow), (3) thickness (at least 3 mm), (4) presence of air- bulbs (especially the elongated forms and position of the air-bulbs, e.g. in the lower parts of the object), (5) weathering features (craquelé, iridizing, corroded surface) and (6) surface patterns (wavy patterns, unevenness, small holes).

In case a fragment has at least five of the six properties, it was categorized at 75%. In case a fragment has at least four of the six properties it was categorized 'likely' (50 %). In other cases the fragment was labeled 'incerto'.

Partially, glass fragments were determined with help of other glass fragments which were determined as Roman, especially the window pane glass which is rather easy to recognize. Other fragments with same appearance and features were in such case classified as 'very likely'.

This whole system to validate the fragments is arbitrary and only can be referred to as some frame to give these finds a place between other finds from the same location.

Details of some glass fragments.

U12. A translucent glass fragment with partial craquelé weathering as surface disintegration. The craquelé is present at one surface only and has not entirely penetrated the glass fragment, so the opposite site is still intact. This is an example of impact at a flat surface (Iben, 2007)

13. A small glass fragment, translucent pale yellow in color, with one rounded side, probably this is also a fragment of window glass. One side however has a slight concave surface, which makes it also possible this fragment is belonging to a utensil.

W 9. A piece of flat, translucent green glass, with two matt surfaces. One surface is showing numerous microscopic parallel lines, the other has a mottled structure, where loess particles are adhered with the rough surface spots

16. Melted glass fragment, with lumpy appearance, in intense bluish green color, containing numerous relatively thick air bulbs and a rough, bumpy surface. The glass fragment is 'polluted' with a deep cobalt blue glass fragment, elongated in shape, melted at the inside.

U 31. Fragment of square bottle in very pale green bluish color, with lower wall (th. variable between 1,1 – 2,0 mm ; 1,1 mm is measured in the concave corner) descends vertically. With rounded edges on the outside.

U 33. Translucent very light yellow brownish glass fragment with deep craquelé effect. The craquelé is visible at all sections. It is partially showing a parallel line pattern, suggesting this has not been caused by one impact point.

Following fragments, listed below are probably not Roman:

U 19. Bottom fragment in translucent very light green color; vertical wall variable in thickness (1,1 mm – 3,9 mm) with concave edge at the inner side and rounded edges at the outside.

U 29. Rim fragment of a bottle in translucent very light greenish color; vertical wall th. 2.0 mm, horizontal rim part th. 2,5 mm, extended rim part (horizontally) 2,3 mm and extrapolated diameter inside 0.95 cm, outside 1,9 cm. Probably related with U30, similar glass type.

U 30. Bottom fragment in translucent very light greenish color, with vertically descending round shaped wall (th. 3,0 mm). Extrapolated bottom diameter is ca 4,7 cm. Probably related with U29.

50. Asymmetric glass bead with tiny bronze drawstring at the inner side.

6.3 Metal from B4

Metal objects from the surface are determined as 'Roman' in case this is justified by its typical shape, which is known from a dated Roman context. Another strong implication for the Roman period is the direct link with the typical dark finds containing local soil type. The finds include nails and tools.

Besides of some objects in bronze and silver cf., many iron objects have been collected, all of them in heavily corroded condition. Description of iron objects see paragraph 6.3.2.

6.3.1. Bronze, lead and silver objects from B4

As expected, hardly any (semi-precious) metals such as bronze, copper, silver were found in the examined area, considering the many times people with metal detectors searched here. During the prospections many surrounding areas were frequently visited by detector -amateurs. The few non-ferrous finds are reported here for completeness.

*Figure 45 Image left: a bronze fragment, middle a silver (cf.) object and right a small piece of lead
Image right: a curled bronze fragment, probably from a fibula*

Figure 46 Copper alloy (attachment) button from B4.

Figure 47 Small part of a bronze spiral fibula from B4

Figure 48 Iron nail with high percentage of bronze, hardly showing any iron dioxide, but some dark green gloss due to copper alloy. Only find of nail in this alloy.

6.3.2. Iron objects from B4

Contrary to the semi-precious metals, iron objects were found plenty, especially linked at the dark soil type.

A total of ... iron finds were made at location B4, mainly square wrought iron Roman nails. and a tetrahedral iron spear point of a Roman catapult (see e.g. Campbell, 2003). Following iron objects could be identified:

a. Iron nails. This is the largest group of iron objects from B4.

b. Fixation hooks, T shaped nails, image 3, 4, 5

A comparative find of an iron T- shaped nail was made in Heerlen, depicted in the iron objects and tools group (Jamar, 1977 pp. 39/d) and is also known from Wroxeter, Shrewsbury Museum, see internet reference 3.

c. fixation hooks . image... 1

d. chain parts , typical eight shaped chain parts image.... 7

e.

Figure 49 : iron objects from B4 attributed to the Roman period/ medieval period. Left a large series of handmade wrought square iron nails. Numbers: 1 = hook 2 = chisel, probably Roman 3-5 T-shaped nails 6 key? 7 chain fragment 8 iron ring 9 spiral on nail 'art object'? 10 pick adze, period uncertain

Figure 50: 72 iron objects from B4: indeterminate (iron nails etc. but uncertain for its period. It is likely several square iron parts belong to nails from the Roman period).

Figure 51: iron objects from the post-Roman period (?) Left is a hinge.

Figure 52 Iron Roman arrow point from B4. This point measures 73 mm over all and is 13 mm wide (max). It weighs 31 grams

Figure 53 Lateral view of an iron object from B4. In the middle part there is a hole, which is almost closed by corrosion. Dimensions: length 95 mm, wide average part: 4 mm, width in middle section: 22 mm, thickness 6 mm; biased by corrosion. Period is uncertain

6.4. Metal slag from B4

In the limited zone of the dark soil type, many slag fragments were noticed and partially collected to get an idea about the type of slag. It seems these are ferrous and non-ferrous slag fragments.

Figure 54 Metal slag (iron) from B4. The biggest slag with weight of 445 grams

6.5. Bone from B4

Bone material, found at the surface, usually is a very unreliable in terms of the period.

The collected bone fragments sometimes have intense glossy patinas, probably indicating a higher date, but still the relation with other finds is unclear. A fragment of antler bone with cutting marks has been found at B4, located in the dark soil type, with possible link to the Roman period (?).

Figure 55 Figure left and right: antler bone with cutting marks at one side, evidence for anthropogenic use

6.6. Natural stone from B4

7. Finds from location B5

The location B5 is adjacent to the investigated area of B4.

This field is the continuation of the field B4 and only separated by a road named *Veltjensweg*.

The location has been prospected in 2014.

The following finds have been listed from B5:

7.1. Flint artefacts from B5

Three flint tools have been found, and this number is relative low regarding the location which must have been between former water wells. Two artefacts are made of non –local honey colored flint type, and one is made of local flint. For descriptions and image, see appendix 8.

7.2. Iron objects from B5

Three iron objects were found, one round shaped hook, a chisel or large nail and a concave circular metal object.

Figure 56 Iron objects from location B5

7.3. Pottery from B5

The following pottery shards have been listed from field B5

Roman period 2 shards

Figure 57 Roman shards from B5

Medieval: 4 shards

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Figure 58: 4 shards of medieval pottery

7.4 Burned clay from B5

Two fragments of burned clay were found.

Figure 59 burned clay "loam type ; 'huttenleem'

*Figure 60 Front and back view of shards of coated red ware, similar to finds from
Leverkussen - Rheindorf in Germany (Frank, 2011)*

Part 3 TESSERAE FOUND AT A LOCATION ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROMAN VILLA VLENGENDAAL IN BOCHOLTZ, (COMMUNITY OF SIMPELVELD, NL)

12. Tesserae: an introduction

At the location B4 (= Bocholtz 4, see for other information part 1 in this report)), which appeared to be adjacent to the remains of a former Roman villa in the southeast of Bocholtz ,in a typical very dark colored soil type, many mosaic stones and glass tesserae (gr.: τέσσαρα: „four“= four -sided stones) were noticed. These tesserae appeared at the surface of a plowed field, not far from the location where a Roman villa has been excavated in the twentieth century, known as “the villa of Vlengendaal” (Goossens, 1912; Wolters & Bonten, 1998; De Grooth, 2007). Tesserae best could be regarded as ‘ceramic building material’ (Jeneson, 2013), the building stones of Roman mosaic.

This Roman villa has been constructed in the first part of the second century AD and was inhabited till the first half of the third century (De Grooth, 2007). The villa terrain had a surface of ca 125 x 60 m and some different buildings were noticed: a main house and two outbuildings.

It appeared the villa had been highly decorated by floor mosaics and wall paintings (Goossens, 1916; Swinkels & Moormann, 1980), suggesting the owners would have been wealthy. Goossens mentioned the mosaic found in room G, originating from a decoration in a bathroom, was very colorful and consisted of an ornament, mainly in geometric figures, while room C had a mosaic decoration at the wall, consisting of a zone of ca 8 cm wide mosaic pattern (Goossens, 1916). After the extensive early twentieth century excavations, a *leftover* of archaeological correlate remained at the surface, which probably has not been of much interest, most likely because it is *ex situ*. Another reason could be, the leftover is part of the archaeological correlate of the not very much investigated area '609/1178' (Goossens, 1916). On the other hand, it is obvious that about one hundred years after the excavations took place; this correlate is absolutely not completely and has been prospected many, many times, especially by metal detecting methods (only two small bronze fragments were noticed by the naked eye) and probably by field surveys, so it is remarkable, how many of the archaeological correlate still was left in the field. In this context of a plowed soil, many artifacts were noticed during field inspections in 2009 / 2010 and in 2014 - 2015. Such short, intensive repeatedly approach of a field survey at a very limited area can provide much additional information on existing knowledge and sometimes even bring new information (e.g. De Haas, 2011) or give better prediction models for human settlements and land- use by landscape classification (Feiken, 2014). This report focuses on two artifact groups from this leftover, the *stone and vitreous tesserae*, which are often hard to find at the surface and several glass finds, attributed to the Roman period, discovered in special targeting field surveys focused on tesserae and glass, carried out in 2010 and 2014. As I am absolutely no glass specialist, some explanation about attribution of such finds to the roman period is required. The immediate context with the adjacent excavated Roman villa (terrain) can be cleared by many typical, easily determinable additional finds from the Roman period (mainly pottery shards, Roman roof tiles that also appear sometimes with a blue core, some fragments of marble, iron nails), so the information from these objects could fit in the existing information about this specific location. Moreover, other objects found at this location easily could be placed into the sub-recent period, after the excavations (late nineteenth century- recent). Tesserae are relatively unknown phenomena in the Dutch Roman record and are only reported from Simpelveld – Vlengendaal (Goossens, 1912) and from Ewijk – *De Grote Aalst* (Blom, Van der Feijst, & Veldman 2012; Van Enckevort, 2012). **In the context of villa Vlengendaal, they were found together with some wall -painting fragments** which are relatively small and are described in a forthcoming report (Groen, 2016). **Similar painted wall fragments were described by Moormann and Swinkels (Moormann & Swinkels 1980). The importance of finds of tesserae is underlined by Vanhoutte and Vanderhoeven at the website of Onderzoeksbalans Onroerend Erfgoed Vlaanderen (see internet reference 4), where even single finds of tessera are assigned as important.** As the tesserae are the building stones of mosaic decorations which has been gone lost, the information in this article is focused on the individual building blocks; suggestions about the original designs of the mosaics are entirely hypothetical. At the same field, many glass fragments were found, these are described in the second part of this report. The only reason for the writing this part of this report is sharing information about regional archaeological finds, in this case paying attention to underexposed artifacts that are easily overlooked in the field and might be of interest.

12.1. Tesserae: methods

Because this report focuses on reporting of characteristics of the tesserae, their colors, dimensions, shapes and possible original position in the matrix have been examined.

As the shades of colors of Roman glass tesserae are almost infinite (Sear, 1997), the diversity range would only tell something about the complexity of a design; the dimensions can tell us something about the period they were manufactured REF, the angles might indicate the use of curves and patterns in the original design REF. Numbers of stone and vitreous tesserae might

Regularity of dimensions of stone tesserae might tell something about its period (of production) REF, where more regular forms existed before the introduction of mass production of tesserae in the first

century; the dimensions of colored glass tesserae could tell something about how extremely fine a work has been performed [REF](#). Dimensions also could tell something about the complexity of a design caused by shape, size, coloration, and texture of the pieces (Dunbabin, 1999). The size of tesserae might also tell something about its basic design in a mosaic, e.g. faces and hands were performed by smaller cubes than background and drapery (Wilson, 2013). Other derived indications about the relation between size and shape are for example circles, that where made of tesserae smaller in size, as visible in a square fragment with central decoration from Abbots Ann, Hampshire, (described by Asprom, see internet reference 5) and rectangular shapes block the possibilities to make curves. The vitreous tesserae are all counted and measured, while from the black variant and white stone tesserae a representative random sample of 100 individuals for each group has been examined for their dimensions, for the presence of remains of mortar and the occurrence of oblique sides. Several stone tesserae still bear traces of adhering mortar at one or more sides. The mortar composition has been examined at a macroscopic level by means of a binocular with magnification up to 5x.

12.2. The tesserae from Bocholtz VA: properties and dimensions

Tesserae are generally square in shape and are forming the small building stones of mosaic panels and floor - mosaics, which decorated certain buildings during the Roman period, especially buildings for the rich or special buildings (Wightmann, 1985: 138; Dunbabin, 1999)

Different stone or glass pieces were cut into small cubes and arranged into representational designs and geometric patterns. So the tesserae were preformed in cubic shapes, re- shaping was required in order to ensure that the stones would fit, e.g. in wavy patterns as in *opus vermiculatum* (see for more information e.g. Hetherington, 1967; Cartwright 2013). Stone tesserae were made of e.g. marble or chalk (Tasker, et al., 2011), (roof) tile or pottery parts, or even made by natural stones and are involved in a process of recycling materials. ([REF](#)) Glass tesserae were made of clear colored and opaque glass (the latter called *smalti*). Tesserae were imported and exported from different quarries throughout the Roman Empire and changed during the Roman period (Flügel and Flügel, 1997; Reghizzi, et al., 2014). The found tesserae in Bocholtz range in size, color and material. To find out the original position of individual tesserae in a mosaic, the remaining cement on the individual blocks in combination with polished surfaces were taken as a reference for width, length and thickness.

This, because more or less oblong tesserae also occur and in such case it is also possible they were placed at one side in the longitudinal direction, like it was the case in the mosaics from an old Roman port, Ostia Antica. The sizes of the stone tesserae can tell something about the period they were produced/ used, as from the mid- first century AD and onwards, the tesserae were averaging 0.8 cm and 1.0 cm in size, and were less regular in shape larger than previously, due to mass-production (Dunbabin, 1999).

12.2.1. Stone tesserae

The big part of tesserae finds are the stone tesserae, usually in black and white. In the targeted field prospection of 2010, a total of 602 black (N= 406) and white (N= 196) stone tesserae were found, so in ratio of ca. 2:1. The total weight of black stone tesserae was 830 grams and of white stone tesserae 388 grams. So a total of 1.218 kg stone tesserae have been collected, approximately corresponding with an image in size of one A4 sheet. Within this black and white tesserae group several hues appear, in more expressive shades of white, grey or black. The polished surface of mainly the white tesserae is still visible at several individuals, but certainly not at all. The white tesserae are creamy white and made of limestone.

Not all tesserae are cubic in shape. Triangles and half cut stones in various sizes also occur: see image below.

Generally there are two major groups regarding the dimensions of both black and white tesserae, either averaging 10 x 10 x 9 mm or 6 x 6 x 5 mm. This second group of smaller tesserae is more regular in shape (more 'nice' square in form) and occurs in much smaller numbers compared to the first group with bigger dimensions.

Figure 61 Variation in size in the black stone tesserae group.

12. 2. 2. Vitreous tesserae

Vitreous (opaque) colored tesserae occur in minor quantities (N= 86, ca 12,5 %) in the total group of found tesserae (N= 688) of the field prospection of 2010. Glass tesserae were predominantly used in wall mosaics or played an additional role in floor mosaics, only if colors (especially green and blue) were indispensable in the designs as glass based tesserae are less durable than stone (Dunbabin, 1999). Only few of the colored tesserae occur in similar sizes with the black, white and red colored stone tesserae (all about 1 cm³), so usually they were less big and much more irregular in shape. They are mainly green to bluish in color, but also grey shades and black and white opaque tesserae occur (see image below). One tessera has a translucent, magenta color.

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Vitreous tesserae and tesserae of tile fragment and polished marble (9 and 10)

Figure 62 Colored glass tesserae in various colors 1-18, except for 10 which is white polished marble 1-5 green variants, 6 = black (shiny) 7 grey- brown 8 white 9 red pottery based 11-13 hues of grey 14-18 different variants of turquoise and blue- green

The dimensions of a selected group of the vitreous tesserae from the seasonal prospection of 2010 (N= 86) are ranging between and 3 x 2 x 2 mm minimum and 10 x 9 x 8 mm maximum. The average sizes were: length 8.159 mm, width 6.318 mm and thickness 4.829 mm. The average thickness of the tesserae is biased by the 2 mm range which is in reality not the thickness but the width. When the records with 2 mm thickness are corrected by the corresponding dimensions of width, the average dimensions for thickness is 5.023, which is very constant, compared with length and width. From nearby locations black opaque tesserae were reported, namely from two sites in Trier (D) (IIIa-c AD Sear ,1977; - IIIId-IV AD Sear, 1977).

Dimensions of vitreous tesserae, unbiased, are showing the strong 5 mm line. The 2 mm range is in reality not the dimension of the thickness, but its width (so the tessera has been put at its side); in that case, the thickness is in line with the 5 mm.

Block diagram with the repartition of numbers of vitreous tesserae based on color (N= 86)

In the block diagram above it is clear the green variants colors are in majority they form 60, 4 % of the total. If bluish green is considered a variant of the green, the number of green variants is even 80, 2 %. It is remarkable, *white and black* tesserae also occur as vitreous tesserae besides of the commonly used stone tesserae in these shades. It is unknown if this means we deal with a different *opus tessellatum*, as combinations of both tesserae types were often combined in floor mosaics, especially in the centre piece in pavements with more simple, geometric designs, (see e.g. Bacchus, god of wine from *via Flaminia*, Rome. (Palazzo Massimo, Rome).

The black glass tesserae found in architectural decoration in Italy and France, were generally used to decorate wall mosaics within fountains and bath structures of the villa complexes of wealthy citizens and emperors (Cosyns, 2011).

The white tesserae are also known from sites throughout the Roman Empire. In a thermo-analytical approach, Bairo and Quaglia found that in white tesserae, which were in excellent state of conservation, the opaque white colour characterizing the surface appearance was not homogeneously distributed in the whole material volume. (Bairo F., Quaglia A. (2012). In a macroscopic examination of the opaque tessera from Bocholtz,

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Comparison in average dimensions of length, width and thickness in four vitreous tesserae groups.

In the diagram above, it is visible that the average length of the vitreous tesserae is the most variable by color, ranging between 7,2 and 9,0 mm, so 1,8 mm in difference. The thickness is the less variable by color, ranging between 4,9 and 5,4 mm , so 0,5 mm in difference.

When we compare the dimensions of stone and vitreous tesserae (COMP in final version)

A very tiny green opaque glass fragment measuring 3 mm by 3 mm is the smallest find of the opaque glass (see image below).

Figure 63: Small tessera fragment, with crusted loess (magnification x 4)

Most vitreous tesserae are in relative good condition, though macroscopic views show the surface often is pocked, wherein the small dimples occur and frequently are filled up with adhesive loess particles (see image below).

Figure 64 Deteriorated surface of a green vitreous tessera, caused by influences of the damaging of alkaline components of the glass, most likely caused by fertilizing. Magnification 4x

12.2.3.. Tesserae made from pottery/ tile (ceramic)

In addition, two red colored tesserae originating from pottery or tile occur; the limited quantity of this color is definitely highly influenced by the presence of so many small roof tile parts which would have disturbed the general view in the field.

Red tesserae were made of terracotta which must have been a cheap and convenient material compared to imported red stone tesserae, like in Britain (Rook, 2013).

Figure 65: Two red colored tesserae made of pottery

12.2.4.. Some special tesserae in the group

The first special find in the tesserae group is a translucent blue- green square tessera in size 10 x 10 x 8 mm. It has the same concavity at one side as usual at many black and white tesserae. Inside, many air pockets are visible, and a small part is polluted. As all dimensions of this object are identical to the dimensions of main part of the tesserae from the location, there is no doubt this glass object could be confused with just a glass fragment with similar dimensions.

Figure 66: A rare blue green translucent square cubic tessera; in detail the surface of the glass tessera, revealing an accumulation of air bulbs and parallel circle shaped features, both involved in the production process

The second unique find is an opaque glass red colored tessera with black parallel lines, measuring ca. 10 x 9 x 8 mm. It is supposed, such red tesserae are composed from a mixture of two sand sources or glass types or it has been influenced by the addition of extra ingredients added to give it its red colour and opacity (Smirniou et al., p. 74 / table1, tessera 9). This ingredient, used as a pigment often contains lead, zinc or tin (see e.g. Entwistle and James, 2013). The parallel lines also could indicate the tessera has been re- used, as the process of making such parallel lines could go back to twisting, like is known from glass beads.

Figure 67 A rare red opaque glass tessera with black parallel line inclusions, top view and side view and magnification of the details of the black lines, (4 x magnification).

A third single find in the tesserae group is an opaque cobalt blue tessera.

Figure 68 Cobalt blue tessera from B4

12.4. The mortar related with tesserae

Usually, the cement for mosaic tesserae were hydraulic mortars that contained lime and a pozzolan such as brick - marble or volcanic dust and water, forming a fluid mixture that could resist over very long time, which is proved by the recently found tesserae, still bearing the adhering mortar on

several surfaces. Though many tesserae carry the white pattern of a very fine embedding mortar at one or more sides, only one tessera in particular still carried a *nucleus* part of the mortar, which was big enough to examine.

In a macroscopic examination the composition of the nucleus was (taken from a black cubic tessera): lime; translucent quartz, ca 2 mm in size; small yellow quartz < 1 mm fragments of orange colored material, such as pottery (terra cotta/ tile fragments cf). See picture below.

Figure 69 Cement adhered to a black cubic tessera. For a description of the mortar see text.

The use of fragments of potshards is known from Roman concrete, but also from light mortars for mosaic; in the Dionysos mosaic of Cologne the original laying bed was described as made of mortar and potshards powder (Femersdorf, 1956) and it was common to use potshard or broken tile in the nucleus part of the mosaic mortar (Corso and Romano, 1997).

In the field, both the upper fine structured mortar (sometimes referred to as the *setting bed*) has been noticed and the underlying more crude pottery mixed mortar, which forms the *nucleus*.

To fix the tesserae, very fine white cement has been used; maybe this was also worked in to fill the crevices between the tesserae. See for mortar types Appendix M2 at the back of this report.

Figure 70: White cement on tesserae, revealing their original place in a mosaic framework; the thickness of the embedding is ca 0,35- 0,50 mm for tesserae in transverse position and up to 0.8 mm for upright positioned tesserae

Figure 71: Examples of tesserae with adhering mortar

12.5. Tools to adjust tesserae in size: is there evidence for onsite size adjustment?

Roman mosaic floors were often partially pre- fabricated as *Emblemata* and thus could be transported over long distance. A part of the work however was carried out in situ (Rook, 2013). Small sized and pointed hammers (so called *martellines*) were used to adjust the size of the tesserae. In this method, a piece of material is held against the *hardie* (a thick chisel piece, with a wider bottom and smaller top, embedded in a wooden log, to form an anvil part) at right angles in the position of a desired fracture and then struck by the opposing hammer with a single, light touch which will create a clear fracture without splintering. The comparative signs of such hammering, small curved cutting marks left by a small pick, are still visible at several sides of the tesserae, found at B4. These marks always appear at only one side, in a 90 degree angle.

To prove this possibility the dimension and shape of the concave cutting mark at the side of the tessera is compared with the shape and dimensions of the suggested tool, used in this process. One iron tool was noticed in the same context with the tesserae and it is quite well possible it has been used for the final adjustment of the stone and glass tesserae *at the location*.

A small piece of iron with chamfered corners and wider base has been found at the same location, which might be interpreted as an accompanying *hardie*. This small object weighs 40 grams and is 38 mm long, 13 mm wide (base) , 7 mm wide (top) and the thickness is 11 mm at the base and 6 mm at the top. The iron of this object is very dense in structure and shows less oxidation, compared to other iron objects from the same field. This combination justifies the hypothesis; these tools most probably could have been used for the final adjustment to make the tesserae fit in the prepared mosaic structure.

The vitreous mosaics, could very well have been imported as real *emblemata* (transportable limestone slabs) since their iconographical richness and invested technique, required more time and concentration, which was not carried at the building site. Still it could have been necessary to carry out repairs, for which tasks tools were required. Current tools for the making of mosaics do have the same shape: these are half -moon shaped picks where mosaic stones are adjusted in size on a small iron anvil. Though the finds of the iron tools have been made in the vicinity of the tesserae, still these are surface finds, so we must be very carefully with interpretation and other applications are also possible for these tools. Another possibility is, the small pick axes were (also) used for the preparation of a mortar embedding for the tesserae. The reason this tool is presented here is, there is little knowledge about its real function and interpretation of such tools is poor (Allason-Jones, 2011), so a study at the function of such tools could spread new light on this subject.

Figure 72 A-typical possible Roman iron double sided, pointed axe (front and back view), found in the same context of the tesserae. It is clearly visible the axe has been used; probably it has been used for the preparation of the tesserae bed. The wooden handle is decomposed in the soil.

Figure 73 Cutting marks on tesserae, mainly visible in the black stone tesserae group. The concave cutting marks supposes to be caused by a small round-shaped jammer or pick.

12.6. Possibilities and limits in design

Although any representation of a design of the floor mosaics is entirely hypothetical, some partial inferences could be drawn from the found material; only few mosaic parts survived the excavations from 1911-1913 by Goossens, see image below (Goossens , 1916).

In the Roman Empire floor mosaics were decorated in patterns, of which the double strand Guilloche is the most familiar, used in the whole Roman Empire.

During the excavations in 1911- 1913 some parts of the floor mosaic were detected which are relatively small (picture below).

Figure 74: Image above: the original parts of mosaic from Vlengendaal, found at the excavations of 1911-1913; in exhibition at the Thermen museum in Heerlen. In the images below, the edges are illuminated, also showing similar concave shaped edges with cutting marks as drawn in the picture before.

Unlike pictures like found in the villa of Nennig in Germany (south - west of Trier near the Luxembourgian border) the design in the Vlengendaal villa must have been more elementary: with the very limited range of colors, it is simply not possible to create *big*, complex lifelike images.

So the tesserae most likely were used to create a black and white motif with geometric figures see e.g. the sober Third Style pavement type such as found at Oplontis, early Roman, 15 BC- 45 AD, Clarke, 1991). Black and white tesserae from Bocholtz may however also have been depicting simplified special objects in *figural mosaics* like an amphora, a fish, a tree, an elephant or even one or more persons, like known from Ostia Antica or the baths of the House of the Menander at Pompeii (Clarke, 1991). In the appendix 3b3, a simple reconstruction of part of a fish adapted after an example in Ostia's floor mosaics, in black and white is presented, proving this sort of pictures was one of the possibilities.

Furthermore, it is not known whether the glass tesserae have belonged to any design in combination with the black and white tesserae, although Goossens describes the mosaics as very colorful. Black, grey, white and red tesserae are sufficient to perform simple pictures) and a *vermiculatum* technique of the tesserae is established by the many angles at the individual blocks, to create wave patterns.

Another example of a simple design motif we can find from room four of the Roman villa of Poggio Gramignano in Italy, where (cit.) "a poorly preserved mosaic with a pattern of rosettes composed of four white tesserae disposed around a central black tessera arranged in rows on a field of black tesserae..." (Soren & Soren, 1999).

The additional found colored glass tesserae however are suggesting a possibility for more complex imaging patterns in combining opus where the black and white tesserae were functioning as a background (see also appendix B), but finds of white and black vitreous tesserae make it even possible the vitreous tesserae were used in a different, separate mosaic., maybe forming an *emblemata* as a centre piece of a bigger design.

Figure 75: Roman black and white stone tesserae from Bocholtz, put together in an imaginary design of a mosaic.

The number of poorly cut tesserae, with one or more wide angles is relatively high. **This indicates the later mass production of tesserae during the second half of the first century AD.**

The stone tesserae range in size between 0,5 and 1,3 cm (measure method explanation) but when we look at the number of black and white marble tesserae, necessary for a mosaic of 10 x 10 cm, namely 81, it is obvious the average size of an individual is not one cm³.

12.7. The tesserae in wider perspective: the use of tesserae in the Lower Countries and adjacent

In The Netherlands, only the presence of tesserae has been established as no floor mosaics survived. The two locations are known as the roman villa of Bocholtz -*Vlengendaal* and from the roman villa Ewijk – *De Grote Aalst*.

While the Roman villa Vlengendaal already excavated, in 1911 and 1913 knowledge about villa Groote Aalst was first enlarged by means of deep plowing. This has not been the intention, but when the villa was nominated to be legally protected in 1980, the land was deliberately deeply plowed so

many things emerged from the deeper horizons of the villa, such as coins, pottery shards, fragments of wall paintings and... tesserae. This means the find circumstances for the finds of this location are *comparative* with those used for this report, as all these finds come from disturbed contexts, which are directly related to a roman villa. Unfortunately, in both cases the original designs have been lost forever, but this implies the potential possibility of discovering mosaic floors in their original position in roman contexts. Like the *Vlengendaal* villa, the *Groote Aalst* villa belonged to important, wealthy and possibly Romanized inhabitants, using typical Roman cultural customs in their villas, such as the presence of mosaic floors. Floor mosaics are known from Germany. From a Roman villa at Nennig, we know an intact floor mosaic, measuring 15.65 x 10.30 meters, (Schindler, 1921) and from Bad Kreuznach some 'gladiator mosaics' have been excavated (Kohl, 1895; Rupprecht, 1986). Closer to the investigated location at Bocholtz, we find the The Dionysus Mosaic which is presented in the Römisch-Germanisches Museum, Cologne and which dated from the first half of the 3rd century. It covered a floor of a *triclinium* (dining room) in a large villa, comparable with those from Pompeii (Von Elbe, 1995). From Belgium only few locations are known where tesserae have been used to make floor mosaics.

In Kuntich, near Tienen, a reconstruction of a floor of a bath building, was possible on the basis of a substantial number of fragments.(Cramers 1984).

In Tongeren a floor, measuring ca. 3 m x 19 m has been excavated, where a quarter still carried the original image (Vanderhoeven et al. , 1992; Creemers ,1999) . In the vicus of Tienen, a small number of mosaic fragments have been found in the rubble of a bath building, while in a foundation of one of the drainage canals, a large number of individual tesserae was noticed (Vander Hoeven et al,2002).

In a short overview of finds of floor mosaics and individual tesserae from the Flanders part of Belgium (Vanhoutte and Vanderhoeven, article Onderzoekbalans.be) it is explained why floor mosaics are rare for the northern parts of the former Roman Empire: at one hand floor mosaics in these regions were rare during the Roman period. On the other hand there is little excavated. Floor mosaics do not always survive the centuries and are sensitive to soil disturbance.

From Northern France, the Gallo-Roman sanctuary of Grand is famous for its mosaic of 232 m², discovered in 1863, and it is the biggest mosaic of Lorraine and dated in the late first till second century AD (Darmon, 2004).This mosaic has been carried out with a remarkable degree black and white tesserae.

12.8. Tesserae : results and discussion

The tesserae, found at the surface of a field southeast of Bocholtz are not to be considered as isolated, single finds. Its appearance is in relation with the location of a nearby Roman villa that has been excavated and where floor mosaics have been established.

For the period of the found tesserae - as the finds concern surface finds- these might in principle also come from a different period, like the post -roman period. Carolingian glass tesserae are reported from the nearby town of Aachen from ca 800 AD (Keller, Price, and Jackson, 2014).

In this case a Roman date seems to be the most likely option: other finds from the same area are definitely Roman (shards, nails and roof tiles).

Pictures in floor mosaics generally have a background, made of white stone tesserae. So, if not too much biased by the prospection methods, it is remarkable; the black and grey variant tesserae form the majority of the black/ white tesserae.

Even when we regard the fact we cannot say much about the original design where the stone and glass tesserae once belonged to, some preliminary conclusions are possible:

- Many stone and glass tesserae were noticed at a field, adjacent to the place where a Roman villa has been excavated in the early 20th century;
- These tesserae comprise different colors and sizes, and with help of such tesserae, apart from geometric figures, also simple design figures could have occurred in the mosaics, forming a *tesselatum*, comparative to similar known mosaic strategy's, e.g. from Lod, Israel, late 3rd century

AD (Haddad and Avissar, 2003); where the glass tesserae are representing a ‘picture’ while the white, bigger marble tesserae are forming the background and red tile fragment based tesserae a line structure around the mosaic (see internet reference 1).

-Small or very small glass tessera fragments, very irregular in shape, could have been forming some picture by line -drawing, while the marble tesserae were following the design in an *opus vermiculatum*.

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Part 4 SOME COMPARISONS BETWEEN FINDS ASSOCIATED WITH VLENGENDAAL (VA) AND DELLENDER (DA) BASED ON SURFACE FINDS

13. Comparisons between finds associated with two different villa terrains

Comparisons between archaeological sites implicate the use of determined objects and well defined parameters, based on archaeological evidence from similar contexts. Comparisons in archaeology could be made at global scale (e.g. Fletcher, 2005) as well as at very limited, (e.g. as intrasite and intersite spatial (Hietala, 1984; Attema and Schörner, 2012).

After field prospections at two locations, which are directly adjacent to fields that are linked to the remains of Roman villas, a large quantity of archaeological remains is available for some comparisons between the locations adjacent to these two villa terrains.

All finds from Bocholtz - east					
	Dellender associated DA			Vlengendaal associated VA	
Category	B1	DB2	DB1a	B4	B5
Pottery					
Terra sigilata shards					
Course wares shards					
Painted wares shards					
Mortaria shards					
Dolia shards					
Handmade pottery shards					
Glass					
Melted fragments					
Square bottle fragments					

target has changed into the collection of fragile materials such as glass and pottery as sources of archaeological activities, which is very time - consuming.

For the pre- roman occupation of the area, it is clear the region east of Bocholtz has been inhabited or at least has been visited during the Stone Age period, demonstrated by several finds of flint tools, with, as expected, a strong precondition in landscape elements. The finds of these flint tools were predominantly made at sloping foothills with moved colluvial horizons nearby visible large depressions in the landscape, probably signifying the dominant role of (running) water in former spring areas during prehistory.

A twisted opaque glass bead from the late *La Tène* period proves human activity and presence in the late Iron Age. This may also be derived from finds of many fragments of handmade pottery, found at three locations (B1, DB1a and B4) suggesting local activities near or at the Roman villa's. On the other hand, such finds of handmade pottery at Roman period sites are diffused by blending of indigenous people, which were locally indirectly or directly attached to life at the Roman villa.

For the two known villa terrains east of Bocholtz, some remarks can be made from specific finds, described in this paper.

1. For the location associated with the villa Vlengendaal (VA):

In general, many conclusions from the report from Goossens from 1916 can be underlined by several finds from the field. Only some additional information could be given from new finds, as described in this report. At first, it is clear that the archaeological correlate of the villa is still very big. Thousands of potshards were collected, as well as many other remains that survived the time, such as glass fragments, iron objects. These objects are certainly assured and documented by this report, within the limitations of the study. Other tentative conclusions can be listed here.

A large amount of iron slag in small concentrations, limited to the dark soil type (interpret as an old activity horizon from the roman period) would suggest large local forge activities. Additionally large amounts of iron nails, limited to the same soil type, could point at a more general use of wood – constructions (in the earliest phase of the building), while the find of an iron spear point, is suggesting local use of (an arrow of) a crossbow.. The find of a small iron pickaxe could indicate local adjusting of stone or opaque glass tesserae. Some other iron objects include typical eight -shaped chains and iron objects for the constructions, like fixation of marble plates, (wall -) hooks, a chisel and an iron nail with twisted wire, as some sort of screw.

2. For the location associated with the villa Dellender (DA):

In general, finds associated with Dellender are located over a rather big area at several nearby fields adjacent to the location where excavations took place in 1992. So the roman activity zone is either more large or erosional processes / plowing activities bring up more material over at a large surface. An interesting find is a glass gaming counter that usually turns up in military settlements.

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Online reference collections for pottery

[Potshard atlas of Roman pottery](#)

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Kent Archaeological Society; Dartford District Archaeological Group (DDAG)

[The Christopher St John Breen Medieval Pottery Archive An aid to identifying shards from excavations](#)

Medieval Pottery Research Group [Ceramics Reference Collection](#)

Appendices

A. Table vitreous tesserae: dimensions in whole millimeters

	length	x width	x thickness	
Black	8	7	6	
Black	10	6	5	
Blue-green	10	9	6	
Blue-green	9	6	6	
Blue-green	9	6	5	
Blue-green	6	6	6	
Blue-green	5	5	6	
Blue-green	8	5	5	

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Blue-green	6	5	5
Blue-green	7	6	5
Blue-green	8	5	4
Blue-green	8	6	3
Blue-green	6	5	5
Blue-green	6	5	5
Blue-green	10	11	5
Blue-green	8	5	3
Blue-green	7	5	2
Blue-green	6	5	2
Blue-green	6	5	2
grey blue	9	6	5
grey blue	6	6	6
grey blue	9	7	6
grey blue	8	6	6
grey blue	10	6	5
grey blue	10	7	5
grey blue	10	7	5
grey blue	6	6	6
grey blue	7	6	5
grey blue	9	7	5
grey blue	8	6	3
grey brown	7	6	5
grey brown	7	6	6
grey brown	9	8	5
white	10	9	8
green+var	10	7	6
green+var	10	6	5
green+var	10	9	5
green+var	10	6	5
green+var	10	6	6
green+var	10	8	6
green+var	11	9	5
green+var	7	7	6
green+var	10	6	5
green+var	7	6	5
green+var	10	7	6
green+var	6	6	5
green+var	10	7	5
green+var	10	9	6
green+var	8	7	5
green+var	8	8	5
green+var	8	7	5
green+var	6	6	5
green+var	7	6	5
green+var	6	5	5
green+var	11	6	5
green+var	8	6	2

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green+var	7	7	3
green+var	7	7	5
green+var	10	8	6
green+var	10	9	6
green+var	6	5	4
green+var	9	5	5
green+var	9	8	5
green+var	8	6	6
green+var	10	8	6
green+var	9	8	6
green+var	9	6	5
green+var	10	7	6
green+var	10	6	5
green+var	9	7	5
green+var	6	6	5
green+var	10	5	3
green+var	10	5	4
green+var	10	6	5
green+var	9	6	5
green+var	9	6	2
green+var	10	9	6
green+var	10	5	5
green+var	6	5	4
green+var	5	5	5
green+var	5	4	2
green+var	3	2	2
green+var	7	5	3
green+var	5	3	2
green+var	5	5	3
green+var	5	5	3
red	10	7	7
red	9	8	6
avarage	8,159	6,318	4,829

**B. Table vitreous tesserae,
average dimensions**

average wide black	9
average wide blue	
green	7,352
average grey blue	8,363
average wide white	10
average wide green + var	8,288
average wide red	9,5

C. Example of a possible tessera design (hypothetical)

Example of a possibility in design with black/white tesserae from Bocholtz after a black/ white figure of a fish at Ostia's Antica floor mosaic. The image is approximately 24 cm x 16 cm. Tesserae from Bocholtz are - of course- not cemented.

D. Drawings of iron artefacts from B4 (L. J. Groen)

Iron objects associated with the roman villa Vlengendaal (B4)

Iron square shaped nails associated with the roman villa Vlengendaal (B4)

E. Drawing of a section of field B4 related with finds

In the drawing a global spread of artefacts is visible in relation with the typical dark colored top soil.

Section from south east into northwest at VA; at the highest parts, left ca + 190 a.s.l. , mainly pottery shards (P) occur in light colored loess with large limestone chunks, while at the steepest part of the slope we also find the tesserae (T), iron objects (I), iron slag (IS) and glass fragments (G). In the lowering parts of the slope, we notice scattered finds of glass fragments (G), tesserae (T) and finally pottery shards (P) together with shards with a more recent date. The hatched part of the slope is a relatively thick very dark colored soil, where at some places the light underlying horizon is visible (in the direction southeast).

F. Prehistoric flint tools from field B1.

Find locations of flint artefacts from B1 and B2 on an elevation map by AHN viewer. Red stars represent find locations, which approximately coincide with the + 186 m N. A. P. (a.s.l.) elevation line

Flint tools from B1. 1. Flake with prolonged bulb- scar (visible right in the picture) with pointed edge (visible left in picture). 2. Blade with retouch at both sides, one side has steep retouch, the other a low angled retouch. Two small notches are made at each side. The distal side has been retouched to form a more pointed edge, probably for piercing. 3. Irregular partially cortex bearing blade with a nice regular overlapping retouch at one side. Glossy patinas are visible at this retouched edge 4. Wide flake of *Lousberg*- type flint with expressive bulb- scar feature. From the platform, also smaller flake has been taken and a step fraction is visible right below the platform. No retouch. 5. Large decortication flake, made in a hard percussion technique (bipolar), with prolonged ripples. The proximal part is left in the picture and has been retouched. The scar is in the proximal part, but the bulb is visible at the distal end (right in the picture)

G. Prehistoric flint tools from field B2.

Flint tools from B2.

1. Thin flake with expressive bulb and scar, with steep type of retouch, probably used for scratching. Dimensions: 20 x 20.5 x 2.5 mm
2. Flake with on the ventral surface two negatives of flake removals. It has a very fine retouch at three sides. Dimensions 30 x 32 x 10 mm
3. A small scraper, made on a flake, with two convergent sides, forming a point. At the ventral side a large scar is still visible. The point and one side is carefully retouched, one edge at the point with a small notch. Some retouch at the base could make this artifact also be interpreted as a small point. Dimensions: 22 x 18 x 4.5 mm
4. A small borer/ drill with notched side, made on a decortication flake, with at the ventral side production ripples. The point of the artifact is obviously meant for the use as a borer. The dorsal side is half covered with cortex. Dimensions: 32 x 21 x 5 mm.
5. A small type blade core with six blade removals, struck from a multi platform, with dimensions 20 x 30 x 16 mm
6. Flake; based on the bulb scar features the flake is identified of anthropogenic origin. It has no retouch at the edges, or other signs of modification. Dimensions: 41 x 22 x 5.5 mm

H. Prehistoric flint tools from field B4

Find locations of flint artifacts from B4 and B5, represented by the red stars. Image taken from AHN viewer.

Triangle shaped scraper with partially a bifacial retouch, made on local Orsbach flint.

Primary flake, made in bipolar technique (hard percussion) with partially retouch at the distal end and pronounced bulb of percussion and percussion waves.

Three small flint tools from B4, the left object is not completely certain, in absence of scar. Left: flake with dorsal negative and retouched 'bec'; middle: round shaped scraper with surface retouch; right: flake

I. Prehistoric flint tools from field B5

Three flint tools were found at B5, left image dorsal view, right image ventral view of same artefacts.

From left to right:

Left: Scraper made of non -local flint, dimensions 35 x 32 x d mm. Middle: flint chunk with adapted edges dimensions 52 x 47 x 10 mm. Right: Large flake made of local flint type with variable sized edge retouch at four sides, expressive bulb scar present.

J. Additional images of glass finds from B4

Glass finds from B4: melted glass fragment (16) and utensil glass

Glass finds from B4: utensil glass fragments.

Glass from B4: Roman window glass fragments

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Glass finds from B4, rest group: nr 34 – 49

Two opaque glass beads from B4, were found in the dark colored soil type. The period for these very small objects is unclear.

The first one is an asymmetric blue colored glass bead with tiny bronze drawstring at the inner side. Its dimensions: 5mm length, 6 mm width and 5 mm in section. In magnification, parallel lines are visible at the outer wall of the bead. The drawstring has been corroded, and has been partially unilaterally worn (see image magnification)

Find location B4: Asymmetric glass bead with tiny bronze drawstring.

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*Find location B4:detail of the drawstring, fixation end; corrosion and worn right side.
Magnification 4 x.*

Macroscopic view (front and back) of a hexagonal shaped glass bead from location B4. Though the alternation such as glued loess indicates a higher date for this object, it is unclear if this is a Roman bead. It measures 4 mm in length and 5 mm cross cut. Post roman hexagonal beads usually are more large, while Roman hexagonal beads commonly are green in color (Guido , 1978)

K. Miscellaneous objects and pottery shards from the locations

K1. Location B1

No information

K.2. Location B4

Melted glass fragment on lime (image left), with effluxed glass structure in blue and white, visible by magnification 2 x(image right). Its period is uncertain.

Two bottom shards from different pots in smooth fabric, left with grid, right with some letters .RA

Drain pipe fragment from B4, similar shard with finds from B1

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Three shards from B4. Top : shard of an early stoneware jug, ca 15th century; right below: a shard with square shaped incised pattern; left below: shard of Pingsdorf type pottery, ca 12th century

German bullet shell with inscription 37 P490 S 2

37 = manufactory year = 1937 P490 = code of manufactory fabric = Hugo Schneider A.G., Werk Altenburg; S * = brass case 2= batch number

L. Coarse ceramics/ building materials

L1. Wall decoration parts

The fragment is flat 6 mm in thickness (but probably longitudinally broken) and consists of lime/mortar, with one prolonged thin, red colored line .

Painted (wall?) fragment with a tiny line in red

Painted wall fragment from an edge, with line decoration in white and red. At the left side typical mortar is visible, maybe for the decoration with tesserae or other small brick wall ornaments.

Dimensions: length: max 70 mm and width max 62 mm and thickness 16 mm. Detail of the painted wall fragment, showing yellow paint -stains in the part of the white area of the line

L2. Mortar types and parts

A white mortar found in the vicinity of the tesserae; left the lower base part of the mortar and right the upper, fine structured mortar.

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Mortar from B4, with ingredients of lime, tile brick, sand (quartz) and small fragments of mica.

Structure and distribution of the particles in the mortar of previous image

A piece of mica with attached cement, found at B4. Since the white calcareous cement is present at all sides of the object, it has been part of a lime based mortar.

L.3. Floor tile fragments

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A fragment of a roman floor tile (type "Sesquipedalis"?) has been found at B4. It has one smooth and one course surface. It has been partially baked in a reducing atmosphere, for water tightness. The fragment measures: max length 65 mm, max width 50 mm and 28 mm thick. This floor tile type usually has been used in raised floors of the hypocaust (Betts, 1984/ 1985)

Floor tile fragment from B4, top view and side view. In section, a dark grey part is visible, due to reducing baking. Dimensions: length max.70 mm, width max 50 mm, thickness 28 mm.

Tile fragment with two smooth polished sides; in a cross cut view the inner core seems to be more dark red colored. Dimensions: length max 70 mm. wide 55 mm and thickness 25,5 mm

Typical tile fragment with grooves from a hypocaust, found at B4. Dimensions: length max. 70 mm, width max 44 mm , thickness 13 mm

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A thick painted flat ceramic, with unclear function

This is a preliminary report. For some reasons, the final report will not be expected before 2017.